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AI4DI Artificial Intelligence for Digitizing Industry

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1 Executive summary

The present document is a deliverable of the AI4DI project, which is co-funded by the ECSEL Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No. 826060 and ECSEL JU Member States.

This document is intended to give an overview of the types of dissemination and communication activities planned and undertaken during the project lifetime, in order to raise awareness about the project and ensure the uptake of project results. This deliverable is intended to be read together with AI4DI deliverable “D7.19 Draft Plan for Use of the Foreground”, which details the project’s data management plan and the plans for how to introduce the project results in the market.

This deliverable “D7.1 Draft Plan for Use and Dissemination of the Foreground” (Draft PUDF) defines the project dissemination and communication plans and tools to be applied throughout the AI4DI project. This includes, in particular, the following aspects:

- The definition and description of target groups and communication channels
- Tools for dissemination and communication of project results
- Plans for events
- Dissemination and communication activities’ tracking

The framework, consisting of the legal documents – Project Grant Agreement (PGA), Project Consortium Agreement (PCA), and National Grant Agreement (NGA) – and the draft PUDF, form the basis for using, disseminating, and communicating the outcomes of the AI4DI project. In case of any conflicts, the rules defined in the legal documents supersede any rules or recommended practices in the PUDF. In particular, the PCA concerns the consortium internal obligations, while the draft PUDF complements the legal documents by a description of the project-wide dissemination and communication processes, rules and tools to be applied throughout the project. Thus, the PUDF will be the reference document collecting all project dissemination, and communication elements.

The AI4DI project’s Plan for Use and Dissemination of Foreground will be systematically reviewed and updated on the occasion of each consortium meeting in a dedicated timeslot.

2 Introduction & Scope

2.1 Purpose and target group

AI4DI is a large and complex project aimed at developing and advancing artificial intelligence solutions for digitizing industry. Consortium partners work on enabling of performance, industry and humanity by AI for digitising industry is the key to push the AI revolution in Europe and step into the digital age. Existing services providing state of the art machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence solutions are currently available in the cloud. In this project, partners aim to transfer machine learning and AI from the cloud to the edge in manufacturing, mobility and robotics. To achieve these targets this consortium connects factories, processes, and devices within digitised industry by utilizing ML and AI for human machine collaboration, change detection, and detection of abnormalities

2.2 Contributions of partners

Explain which partner were involved and their activities in their various sections

TABLE 1: CONTRIBUTIONS

Chapter	Partner	Contribution
All chapters	TG	Preparation
7.2	OTH-AW	Description of the AI4DI website

2.3 Relation to other activities in the project

This document describes the overall dissemination and communication management of the AI4DI project, including all Work Packages and all Supply Chains. In particular, it provides further guidance to the activities related to WP7 Dissemination, Exploitation and Standardization.

Because this draft Plan will be applied throughout the project duration, it is considered as a 'living document', i.e. it will be enhanced or adapted during the project as required. The first update to this document was included after the first year of the project.

3 Dissemination methodology and target groups

3.1 Key concepts and objectives

The following definitions of the key terms used in this document originate from the European Commission's Participant Portal¹:

Communication: "Communication on projects is a strategically planned process, which starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange."

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/support/reference_terms.html

The general purpose of communicating about European projects is to promote European collaborative research and innovation².

AI4DI project communication objectives are the following:

- Defining an effective communication strategy and target groups (target audiences)
- Creating the common project's visual identity (brand)
- Deploying partners' communication channels, implementing the communication
- Evaluating the communication

Communication will contribute to supporting dissemination and exploitation objectives while targeting stakeholders beyond the immediate interest groups, such as the public at large. Dissemination, per its definition, is “the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.” The dissemination of the project outputs to key stakeholders aims at (1) making the knowledge (results) developed through the project available to the widest audience and (2) enhancing project exploitation potential. Throughout the AI4DI project, communication and dissemination work will enhance public's awareness, inform interested stakeholders, and strengthen the exploitation potential of the created products.

3.2 Definition of target audiences

The target audiences for AI4DI communication and dissemination include industry, regulatory bodies, policy makers, research/academic community, and the wider public. The communication strategy will target all involved, interested, and potential audiences. The consortium will also identify potential interested members who could spread the word of AI4DI key messages, increasing and widening audience participation.

The target audiences for AI4DI can be segmented according to the following criteria, including means of how the consortium will reach those audiences:

Research Community

- *Events:* The consortium will organize a networking event to foster mind-set change to apply AI in the Digitalized Industry. The high scientific profile of the participating academic and research institutes guarantees the success of these special issues, which will demonstrate the project's research achievements worldwide;
- *Workshops organization:* The consortium will organize workshops throughout the project's duration, where interested researchers and industry professionals can go and learn about AI and how to implement it;
- *Contribution to international journals and conferences:* All the interesting and innovative research results of AI4DI will be published in leading international journals in the field, as well as presented to international conferences. It must be pointed out that all principal investigators from research and academia involved in AI4DI comprise well-recognised experts in their field and they participate in wider associations in their fields of expertise, ensuring this way the successful dissemination of AI4DI results and research findings.

² http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/gm/h2020-guide-comm_en.pdf

Industrial and Business Audiences

The AI4DI has a group of industrial partners, SMEs, and public bodies, with strong networking profiles, which will lead the dissemination of the project's outcomes to the industry. This will be achieved through direct dissemination activities such as e-marketing campaigns, news groups, mailing lists / e-Zines (electronic magazines), online press and on-site promotions. Furthermore, dissemination through partners' web sites, with their experiences of this solution and the high level of service provided by the AI4DI platform will be ensured. Exhibitions and participation in specialised events, forums and platforms, in which a number of the project's consortium are prominent members of, will guarantee wide dissemination of the results in EUs scientific and innovative business scenes. Finally, indirect dissemination will be accomplished via consortium partners' public relations, word of mouth, articles and assessment written by independent reviewers.

General Public

- *Traditional Dissemination* including advertising in newspapers, flyers, and periodicals;
- Written articles and papers for publications, engaging in public speaking events;
- Encourage blogger groups to write about the AI4DI solution and establish a social media presence (e.g. Twitter).

4 Dissemination and communication guidelines

To ensure that AI4DI consortium partners are familiar with, and follow the correct procedures when disseminating and communicating information about the project, common Guidelines were prepared. AI4DI Dissemination and Communication Guidelines were developed in a form of a ppt presentation, uploaded onto partner's data-share ownCloud, and presented to the consortium during conference call meetings.

Firstly, the Guidelines describe the concepts of Communication and Dissemination, in the framework of ECSEL JU funding and Horizon 2020 programme. Then the subsequent information follows:

4.1 Acknowledgement of funding and disclaimer

The appropriate ways of acknowledging funding and funding programmes are described in the AI4DI Dissemination and Communication Guidelines. Partners are able to choose the most appropriate form to use to insert into their publications, presentations, and other dissemination and communication means. The following acknowledgement of funding information is used by the consortium:

- Acknowledgement of funding must be included in all AI4DI-related publications and other dissemination material:
"AI4DI receives funding within the Electronic Components and Systems for European Leadership Joint Undertaking (ECSEL JU) in collaboration with the European Union's Horizon2020 Framework Programme and National Authorities, under grant agreement n° 826060."
- Alternative acknowledgement texts:

“The work/A part of the work has been performed in the project AI4DI: Artificial Intelligence for Digitizing Industry, under grant agreement No 826060. The project is co-funded by grants from Germany, Austria, Finland, France, Norway, Latvia, Belgium, Italy, Switzerland, and Czech Republic and - Electronic Component Systems for European Leadership Joint Undertaking (ECSEL JU).”

“AI4DI project has received funding from the ECSEL Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 826060. The JU receives support from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. It is co-funded by the consortium members and grants from Germany, Austria, Finland, France, Norway, Latvia, Belgium, Italy, Switzerland, and Czech Republic.”

- ECSEL JU logo and the European Union flag must be visible next to the acknowledgement of the funding sources:

- National or regional funding authorities must be acknowledged, and their logos included where possible:

- Furthermore, any dissemination and communication activities need to adhere to the specific conditions of EU funding and disclaimer according to Article 38.1.3, which is excluding [Agency and] Commission responsibility. Thus, the following disclaimer must be included in the communication material:

“All AI4DI-related communication reflects only the author’s view and the [Agency and the] Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.”

4.2 Social media posting guidelines

After information about acknowledgement of funding, the AI4DI Dissemination and Communication Guidelines describe where partners can find the dissemination materials (such as presentations, templates, posters). This is followed by **social media posting guidelines**, described below:

AI4DI consortium uses Twitter account **@AI4DI** for social media presence.

What we post: Texts of up to **280** characters. This excludes media attachments (photos, images, videos, etc.) and quoted tweets (displaying someone else's tweet within your own) but includes links (a URL is always altered to 23 characters).

How we use it: To share short comments, make announcements that can instantaneously reach a large audience or retweet relevant content, post pictures from events and videos of demonstrators.

The account is also embedded in the project website www.AI4DI.eu.

The following terminology is important:

Hashtag # - a hashtag is added in front of any word or phrase in a post, this makes it easier for users to locate our specific content. Examples of applicable hashtags are the following: #Innovation, #AI, #futuretechnologies, #industry, #H2020, #ECSELJU. Using a hashtag makes the keyword or phrase in the post searchable. It is like a label that clusters and links similar content, the same way keywords do when scientific papers are published. They are used to increase outreach – enabling us to join bigger, topic-specific conversations, to capitalize on existing trends, to consolidate and group content – helping those who took part in an event search for related coverage using the event's hashtag, to encourage interaction.

Handle @ - unique handle / user name used to identify AI4DI project's account. It always starts with the @ symbol, followed by a name to identify the account: **@AI4DI**. We use handles to mention partner organizations, funding organizations, and related projects, to send a direct reply to someone, by starting our message with their handle, and to link to someone else's account (known as a 'mention') by using their handle in our post.

Tone and general notes that our consortium takes into account when posting in social media:

- Never post pictures or text containing confidential information from consortium's internal meetings;
- Use appropriate, inoffensive language (to ensure we get responses and stimulate debate);
- Be receptive to our readers' arguments – if we don't agree, we can defend our position without being rude;
- Gain/maintain credibility by sharing worthwhile, relevant content and show respect for other cultures and ideas, online as well as offline;
- We must be aware that libel and defamation laws apply;
- We created our **project handle** and use it consistently throughout the overall project implementation;
- If the partners, researchers, team members or other relevant organizations already have a strong, well established social media presence, we encourage them to **communicate information about our** project;
- Use handles, such as **@ECSELJU** and **@EU_H2020** in our tweets to maximize visibility and be recognized as part of the ECSEL JU and H2020 community;
- Twitter is becoming increasingly **visual** – we post pictures, videos or data visualizations to spark interest;

- Share images and **tag other Twitter accounts** (up to 10), to build a relationship with your audience and make them aware (the account tagged receives a notification) of content that might interest them, in the hope that they might want to retweet it.

The following posting schedule is observed for AI4DI Twitter and website posts:

TABLE 2 AI4DI SOCIAL MEDIA AND WEBSITE POSTING SCHEDULE

	Twitter	Website
ON THE DAY OF REGISTRATION TO EVENT	HEADLINE, EVENT DETAILS, LINK	
2 DAYS PRIOR TO EVENT	HEADLINE, EVENT DETAILS, LINK	
DURING EVENT	PHOTOS, LIVE DETAILS	
2 DAYS AFTER EVENT		SUMMARY OF EVENT, RESULTS, PHOTOS
PUBLIC PROJECT RESULTS	HEADLINE, DETAILS, PARTNER INFORMATION	HEADLINE, DETAILS, PARTNER INFORMATION
PROJECT NEWSLETTER	HEADLINE, NEWSLETTER	HEADLINE, NEWSLETTER

4.3 Data Management

In large project like AI4DI with nearly 200 member-users, it is important to enable a smooth operation, safe data exchange and effective management of data among the members. To reach these goals, the AI4DI consortium uses a cloud platform for the data-exchange, where the confidential sharing of files is possible without restrictions.

4.3.1 Data Exchange Platform Nextcloud

The uses cloud software is the so-called “Nextcloud” [**Error! Reference source not found.**], (see Figure below: Screenshot of the AI4DI data share Nextcloud), installed on a server and hosted from the OTH-AW.

FIGURE 1 AI4DI DATA SHARE NEXTCLOUD

4.3.1.1 Access

The Nextcloud-server software supports fully the WebDAV protocol, so users can connect to the server and synchronize their working data. This is possible with every standard browser like, Firefox, Internet Explorer, Opera or Chrome, through the link <https://AI4DI-cloud.automotive.oth-aw.de/> so no additional software is needed to install for the users. It is also possible to access by client applications, which are available for all common Windows, Mac and Linux and furthermore by mobile apps for iOS and Android. It is not necessary to install the apps, but they facilitate the working with files, so they are automatically synchronized properly after saving. The client can be configured to store the data on any local directory.

The files are shared within the project AI4DI, but it is also possible to create personal data, which is not shared.

The file size is partly limited to 512 MB, but can be extended to bigger files if necessary. There are no restrictions for the upload/download speed of the connected users

4.3.1.2 Safety and Security

Within the Nextcloud a version control allows to access to older versions of the files. The Nextcloud software is updated frequently to keep the system up-to-date.

A daily backup is made from all data, which are physically separated from the server. The server is located in Germany at the OTH-AW.

The access to the files is only allowed through the https-protocol [HTTPS]. After the login to the Nextcloud all communication is protected through an SSL encrypted access, verified by a CA-certificate.

4.3.1.3 Mailing lists

Mailing lists for the efficient communication among project partners were set-up; the following lists are available, or will be set up soon:

members@AI4DI.eu (entire Consortium)

core@AI4DI.eu (Project management team)

SC-Leader@AI4DI.eu

WP-Leader@AI4DI.eu

WP1@AI4DI.eu

WP2@AI4DI.eu

WP3@AI4DI.eu

WP4@AI4DI.eu

WP5@AI4DI.eu

WP6@AI4DI.eu

WP7@AI4DI.eu

WP8@AI4DI.eu

The members@AI4DI.eu list is the largest list, with more than 200 users and is therefore restricted in sending for project management team members to avoid the spamming with reply-mails to the users. All other lists are free in the usage and all members can post mails to it.

The members of all lists are daily updated to keep the lists up to date.

4.3.1.4 Server configuration

The web site and the data-exchange platform are hosted on a server located at the OTH-AW (Ostbayerische Technische Hochschule Amberg-Weiden) in Germany, Amberg. The connection provides all needed features like unlimited file upload, not restricted by size or speed. The server has a 1 Gbit/s uplink, which is guarded against failure by a 1Gbit/s secondary backup link. The server is driven by a containerized structure with access through reverse proxies for nextcloud and Joomla. All systems are frequently updated.

The member management for the Nextcloud is combined within the Joomla! backend.

4.3.2 Data privacy and security

The project partners agree that any Background, Results, Confidential Information and/or any and all data and/or information that is provided, disclosed or otherwise made available between the project partners during the implementation of the Action and/or for any Exploitation activities (“Shared Information”), shall not include personal data as defined by Article 2, Section (a) of the Data Protection Directive (95/46/EEC) and applicable local implementing local legislation; or, as from May, 25th 2018, Article 4 of the General Data Protection Regulation. The Data Protection Directive, its implementing local legislation and the General Data Protection Regulation are hereinafter collectively referred to as the Data Protection Legislation.

Accordingly, each project partner will ensure that all data and information contained in Shared Information is anonymised such that it is no longer personal data, prior to providing the Shared Information to such other Parties. Each project partner who provides or otherwise makes Shared Information available to any other project partner, (“Contributor”) represents that, as per applicable Data Protection Legislation: (i) it has the authority to disclose the Shared Information, if any, which it provides to the project partners under the Consortium Agreement; (ii) where legally required and relevant, it has a legal ground to provide the Shared Information; and (iii) there is no restriction in place that would prevent any such other project partner from using the Shared Information for the purpose of this Action and the exploitation thereof.

4.3.3 Open Access publishing guidelines

The AI4DI consortium embraces the vision that large and unrestricted access to knowledge is essential not only for the central role of knowledge and innovation in generating growth but also as a fundamental human value of scientific knowledge progress and dissemination. In line with the “Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020”, the project beneficiaries will aim to ensure open access (‘gold’, or ‘green’) to all peer-reviewed publications relating to the project results. Authors copyright agreements will determine whether scientific publications, resulted from the project, will adopt the gold or the green model. However, in the case copyright agreements are not violated (e.g. in the case of peer reviewed journals and international

conference proceedings), the consortium will favour whichever model guarantees wider dissemination of the project results. Therefore, the Dissemination and Communication Guidelines describe the principles of Open Access Publishing. To comply with the AI4DI project’s Grant Agreement, consortium partners must make their papers and presentations available to the entire consortium ahead of publication; they must be emailed to consortium’s Dissemination Manager or the Core Team.

AI4DI Consortium Agreement states the following: “8.4.2.1 Prior notice of conference contributions and oral-/poster presentations (PowerPoint presentations or similar) shall be given by the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination to by email [...] at least 21 calendar days before submission (contributions) or presentation (presentations). Any objection to such planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement in writing to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 14 calendar days after receipt of the notice. [...] Prior notice of any other planned publication shall be given by the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination by email to the other Parties at least 45 calendar days before submission. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement in writing to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 30 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.”

Consortium partners must follow the review and approval process described in the subsequent process illustration:

FIGURE 2 AI4DI PUBLICATION AND PRESENTATION REVIEW AND APPROVAL PROCESS

Under Horizon2020, each beneficiary must ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results, and AI4DI consortium partners are all expected and informed to follow these rules. Each partner must - at the very least - ensure that their publications can be read online, downloaded and printed. Partners should make every effort to have additional rights such as the right to copy, distribute, search, link, crawl, and mine increase the utility of the accessible

publication. Consortium partners follow the **AI4DI Open Access Guideline Presentation**, which was distributed to the entire consortium and is available on the projects file-share ownCloud. More information is also available at: [Open access & Data management – SEDIA Guide](#)

5 Dissemination and communication strategy deployment

Consortium's initial suggestion is to focus on the following types of activities to communicate and disseminate information about the AI4DI:

Events-based communication: Awareness-raising regarding AI4DI is expected to be impacted positively by active presence in international conferences, workshops, demonstrations is foreseen by all means and tools - and the organisation of at least one micro level event per year. The AI4DI representation will take place in different ways:

- AI4DI will organise physical and virtual events (e.g. AI4DI Bologna Symposium and AI4DI webinars);
- Follow the AI Alliance meetings and having staff present to disseminate AI4DI and providing details and clarifications if needed;
- Participate in major events with targeted stakeholders, using project booth and posters;
- Participation in key events for liaising or networking purposes.

Web-based communication.: Online activities designed as central to the project website and geared completely towards raising awareness and traffic by encouraging more people to visit the AI4DI website;

Print -based communication: newspapers, journals, posters, etc.;

Press Based communication: to multiply the impact of the AI4DI project results towards the different target audiences, we will contact local and international media including newspapers, AI-related magazines and journals, as well as initiatives and individual journalists specializing in the domains in order to encourage stakeholders to share our vision and common understanding of what AI4DI is about;

Audio-visual communication: Prepare a campaign video (simple, for the general public to understand) promoting the project and upload it to the Projects Website, as well as to YouTube/Vimeo and other similar platforms;

Mailings: Promoting AI4DI will be supported by the efficient use of tools such as mailing/distribution lists, which can raise awareness and allow regular contact (e-newsletter).

5.1 Events-based communication

Awareness-raising regarding AI4DI project is expected to be impacted positively by project representation in relevant events. We will represent the project at a number of events aiming to promote the AI4DI outputs and to disseminate by all appropriate means and tools, all relevant information that will raise public awareness about the consortium's work. Participation in events is also an opportunity to increase and strengthen the network of relevant parties interested in becoming multipliers of AI4DI.

Below is a list of some of the events and conferences in the area of transport research, where AI4DI intends to be present during the first year of the project (not and exhaustive list; AI4DI-organised events are highlighted in blue):

TABLE 4 DISSEMINATION EVENTS' CALENDAR

Event name	Date	Location	Notes
Innovation Drift 2019	2019 07 13-14	Vilnius	-
ECSEL JU Symposium 2019	2019 06 17-18	Bucharest	booth, poster
IECON 2019 – 45 th Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society	2019 10 14-17	Lisbon	Publication
EFECS 2019 – European Forum for Electronic Components and Systems	2019 11 19-20	Helsinki	booth, poster
ECSEL–Austria Conference "ECSEL-Austria – A success story moves on"	2019 11 27	Graz	presentation
HiPEAC 2020	2020 01 20-22	Bologna	-
AI4DI Symposium Bologna 2020	2020 01 23	Bologna	presentation, poster, panel discussions
Smart City MINDTREK 2020	2020 01 28-30	Tampere	presentation
24 th Conference on Automation	2020 03 18-20	Warsaw	publication
ECSEL JU Symposium 2020	2020 06 24	online	-
PCIM Europe 2020	2020 07 7-8	Nuremberg	presentation
2 nd Workshop on Closing the Reality Gap in Sim2Real Transfer for Robotics	2020 07 12	online	publications
The 23 rd IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems	2020 09 20-23	online	publication
33 rd International Conference on Industrial, Engineering & Other Applications of Applied Intelligent Systems (IEA/AIE)	2020 09 22-25	Kitakyushu, Japan	publication
European Research and Innovation Days	2020 09 22-24	online	-
LOGIN 2020	2020 09 24	Vilnius	-
IEEE IECON 2020 conference	2020 10 18-21	Singapore; online	publication
EuWoRel 2020	2020 10 21-22	Berlin	-
Industrie 4.0 Conference Kaunas	2020 10 27	Kaunas	leaflet

ECA2030 Conference	2020 10 27-28	online	-
4 th International Conference nanoFIS 2020	2020 11 2-4	online	-
AI4DI 1 st WEBINAR	2020 12 04	online	presentation, success stories, keynote speeches
EF ECS 2020	2020 11 25-26	online	online booth, videos
AI4DI 2 nd WEBINAR	TBD	online	presentation, success stories, keynote speeches
ECS Brokerage Event 2021	2020 01 13-14	online	-
HiPEAC 2021	2021 01 18-20	online	TBD
AI Safety 2020	2021 01	TBD	publication
Design, Automation, and Test in Europe (DATE) Conference 2020	2021 02	online	TBD
AI4DI 3 rd WEBINAR	TBD	online	presentation, success stories, keynote speeches
ESI Symposium	2021 04 20	Veldhoven	TBD
Industry Strategy Symposium Europe (ISS Europe)	2021 04 21-23	Brussels	TBD
Smart Systems Integration Conference and Exhibition 2021	2021 04 27-29	Grenoble	TBD
AI4DI 4 th WEBINAR	TBD	online	presentation, success stories, keynote speeches
ECSEL JU Symposium 2021	2021	TBD	booth, poster
5 th International Conference nanoFIS 2021	2021	TBD	TBD
The 24 th IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems	2021	TBD	TBD
EF ECS 2021	2021	TBD	booth, poster
HiPEAC 2022	2022	TBD	TBD
ECSEL JU Symposium 2022	2022	TBD	booth, poster
LOGIN 2020	2022	Vilnius	TBD
EF ECS 2022	2022	TBD	booth, poster

During the second half of the AI4DI project's first year of implementation, the global COVID-19 pandemic has halted nearly all mass gatherings, resulting in numerous cancellations of planned dissemination and communication events. Consortium partners reacted by creating an ongoing list with planned online events where the AI4DI project will be presented. The list is continuously updated and shared with partners, as well as integrated with the above plan of events.

5.1.1 AI4DI Webinars

Webinars with project supply chains will be organized to report progress and adapt the dissemination strategy according to inputs received and specific needs. Webinars will include a general presentation of the project goals, as well as videos, success stories, and keynote speakers. The first planned AI4DI Webinar will be titled 'AI for Automotive Manufacturing and Mobility-as-a-Service', and the second planned Webinar will be titled 'AI Stories for Industries (Semiconductor, Wood Machinery and Beverage/Food Production)'.

AI4DI Webinars will become the key pillars in the project goal for AI community-building efforts in Europe, being complementary of other initiatives in the related field, and in building and sustaining dynamic AI technology eco systems. The webinars will be open both to the most interested and invested stakeholders, representatives from other consortia, industry representatives, as well as the general public. Webinars are structured to both present the goals, achievements, success stories and the roadmap developed by the AI4DI project, and to entice and facilitate a lively discussion on the technological breakthroughs. The webinars will be recorded and displayed in the project's website, to ensure that interested stakeholders who are unavailable to join the webinar in real-time, can visit the information and discussions at a time that is most convenient for them.

FIGURE 2 INVITATION TO THE FIRST AI4DI WEBINAR

5.2 Web-based communication

During the first months of the project, AI4DI project's website was created by OTH-AW. The AI4DI website is a useful tool to provide in a practical and user-friendly way the project work and dissemination material. Using the www (world wide web) grants access to every member of the project and also gives the public audience a fast and easy way to receive project information. The website is divided in two parts, public information (www.AI4DI.eu) and a project internal data exchange.

Both parts of the website are setup within a flowing process through the project members and will frequently updated with new input, e.g. news of the project, meetings, participation in events, and developments. The website will also be used to provide downloads of the dissemination material.

5.2.1 Website design

The web design was created to fulfil the corporate design, made up by the logo and the visual identity used for the internal and external project communication. This is important for the recognition factor and the continuous solid public image.

5.2.2 Project logo

The AI4DI logo depicts the title of the project combined with an illustration. The overall image is forming a brain shaped logo and at the same showing a circuit board layout. These images are combining the content of the AI4DI project, Artificial Intelligence depicted as brain and Digitizing Industries depicted as the circuits.

FIGURE 3 AI4DI LOGO – COLOURFUL AND MONOCHROME VARIATIONS

5.2.3 Website layout

The layout of the website is derived from a responsive template. It adapts and resizes itself to desktop and mobile devices and provides an optimal handling in viewing and interaction. It is comfortable in its usage for reading, navigation, resizing, panning and scrolling and works with the commonly used range of devices, from desktop monitors.

5.2.4 Website access

The website is accessible through the URL <https://www.AI4DI.eu>. The domain name AI4DI.eu is chosen to connect to the project name AI4DI and the top-level domain .eu, which shows the reference to the European Union (EU).

5.2.5 Public Web Content

The public web content is based on the project contents and its activities. It provides details about the project information as an outcome of the project dissemination and derived from meetings and discussions among consortium members. The intention of the web site is to inform both the public and project members. The supposed visitors will vary from experts in the field, public authorities, industry representatives, researchers, and the general public.

5.2.6 Menus and submenus

The website has the following menu entries on the top site of the web site: Home, News, About the Project, Consortium, Coordinator, and 'Project Data Share' below, to navigate to other parts of the website.

FIGURE 4 HOME PAGE OF THE AI4DI WEBSITE

Furthermore, project's Twitter account was created and is used for posting live updates, project news, and other items. Rules and guidelines for AI4DI posts in social media are described in the section 4.4.3 above.

More detailed information about the AI4DI website is described in Deliverable D7.2 'Project website'.

5.3 Print -based communication

AI4DI consortium's approach is to use the consortium's experience and knowledge of individual groups' needs to develop promotional material that can reflect the project's message and reach its target audiences through the right channels, using the appropriate content and style. The material will carry

the ECSEL JU and AI4DI logos which along with the visual identity will create awareness across the target audiences.

Developing these print-based products in an attractive and high-quality manner requires careful organisation and the inclusion of several sub-processes such as information gathering, analysis, and translation, among others. For this, we have developed the following visualisations, to be used for leaflets, posters, and other print-based dissemination means:

FIGURE 5 BANNER FOR AI4DI GENERAL MARKET PRESENTATION

FIGURE 6 AI4DI VISUALIZATIONS

Together with the website and leaflets, consortium’s posters for presenting results to the interested audience as well as contact information, will be produced. The first version of the project poster has been prepared for the EFCS2019 conference:

AI4DI

Manufacturing

Oil & Gas
Chemistry
Pharma
Semi
Single process

Semiconductor

Silicon Industry

Objectives

Project Artificial Intelligence for Digitizing Industry (AI4DI) will accelerate the Digital revolution in the industry with Silicon-Born-Artificial Intelligence

Technical Innovation

AI4DI will improve/develop the following kinds of technologies:

- Deep Learning in manufacturing and industrial environment
- Ontology management in semiconductor factories
- Smart manufacturing

Relevance and Impact

AI4DI will tackle the following applications:

- Artificial Intelligence on the edge
- Distributed Artificial Intelligence for Internet of Things-devices

Germany INFINEON TECHNOLOGIES AG ALFA AKTIONSGESellschaft FINANZIERUNGSGESellschaft ZÜRICH FOEDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG E.V. TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT DUISBURG TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT MÜNCHEN Carlson Technology Hochschule - Aachen Cognition Factory GmbH Systec GmbH	Italy STMICROELECTRONICS SRL DFCONTROL SRL CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE INTERUNIVERSITARIO PER LA RICERCA ELETTRONICA SCH GROUP SPA	France STMICROELECTRONICS GRENoble 2 SAS COMMISSARIAT AL ENERGIE ATOMIQUE ET AUX ENERGIES ALTERNATIVES TECHNET UNIVERSITE DE REIMS CHAMPAGNE-ARDENNE INSTITUTE POLYTECHNIQUE DE GRENOBLE VERANION-POLYMER/ MEMPHILE	Ukraine UA9 Terebovl YOUNG'S GEORGIAN TECHNOLOGIES UNIVERSITETS	Greece INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY FOR UNIVERSITY LEADERSHIP
Austria ALUETZ GMBH INFINEON TECHNOLOGIES AUSTRIA AG TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT GRAZ Kognitionszentrum - Das Institute für angewandte Forschung gms/gmslab GmbH TTTECH COMPUTERTECHNIK AG INNOVATION CENTER GIBRALTAR RESEARCH CENTER FOR DATA-DRIVEN BUSINESS & BIG DATA ANALYTICS	Latvia ELECTRONIKAS UN ĶĪMISKAJUMI INSTITUTE	Finland INDUSTRIAL TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH INSTITUTE INCORPORATED	Poland MIRVIA ELECTRONICS SP. Z O.O. Technologies i Inżynieria WYBYL LANSZCZY WebSokrates.pl	
Czech Republic VYSOKOSKOLA TECHNICKA BRNO	Belgium INTERUNIVERSITAIR MICRO-ELECTRONICA CENTRUM INTRASOFT INTERNATIONAL SA			

WP/SC matrix	Automotive AVL, ST, Infineon	Semiconductor ST, Infineon	Machinery ST, Infineon	Smart food & Beverage Production Infineon	Transportation Infineon
WP1: Requirements and Specifications for Industrial AI Solutions and Demonstrators, AI Road Maps					
WP2: System Level Design for Industrial AI Solutions					
WP3: AI Methods, Semiconductor Components and ECU Devices					
WP4: Embedded Systems, Edge Computing and Algorithms for Industrial AI					
WP5: Integration and Deployment of AI Applications in Industry					
WP6: Validation, Verification and Tests					
WP7: Dissemination, Exploitation and Standardization					
WP8: Project Management and Projects Clustering					

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Start	Duration
1-09-2019	36
Total investment	404.50
Participating organisations	41
Number of countries	12

FIGURE 7 AI4DI POSTER FOR THE EFCS2019 CONFERENCE

6 Exploitation of the AI4DI foreground

All AI4DI partners have strong interest in participating in this project not-only because it fits with their strategic individual plans but also and mainly because they foresee strong potential for the joint exploitation of the project results and the creation of a sustainable collaboration. They all share the vision of cooperating in a win-win manner. The detailed exploitation plan and use of the AI4DI foreground are described in the deliverable “D7.10 Draft Plan for Use of the Foreground” (CO).

6.1 Intellectual Property Management

For the success of the project it is essential that all project partners agree on explicit rules concerning intellectual property rights (IPR) ownership, access rights to any Background and Results IP for the execution of the project and the protection of IPR and confidential. Details on these aspects were agreed upon in the Consortium Agreement. The establishment of intellectual property and other aspects of innovation in this project are primarily done by the respective work packages. Participants will jointly or individually prepare patent applications for new concepts and solutions, conceived respectively jointly by one or more participant or solely by one participant. AI4DI aims to have patents filed by one or more partners to protect innovations from the project which have the potential to have a significant impact. Innovations, concepts and solutions that will not be protected by patent applications by the participants will be made public after agreement between the partners and per the procedure established in the consortium agreement and referred to below, to prevent others to block usage of these results.

Regarding IPR, the use of the European IPR Helpdesk (www.ipr-helpdesk.org) is promoted to help individual participants and partners with questions related to the protection of IPR. A procedure will be established to inform all other partners in the project when results of the project will be made public (e.g. in a conference paper), allowing partners to protect IPR before publication. The project maintains a record of all related documents and discussions. This can later be used as a base for resolving conflicts related to IPR filings. Foreground IP shall be owned by the project partner carrying out the work leading to such Foreground IP. If any Foreground IP is created jointly by at least two project partners and it is not possible to distinguish between the contributions of each of the project partners, such work will be jointly owned by the contributing project partners. The same shall apply if, in the course of carrying out work on the project, an invention is made having two or more contributing parties contributing to it, and it is not possible to separate the individual contributions. Such joint inventions and all related patent applications and patents shall be jointly owned by the contributing parties. The full details of the legal framework for the project related to the work, IP-Ownership, Access Rights to Background and Foreground IP for the duration of the project and any other matters of the consortium’s interest will be defined in the Consortium Agreement (CA). This will be signed by all partners prior to the project start.

7 Conclusion

Dissemination is defined in the Rules for Participation as “public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium”³.

To ensure a wide dissemination and communication, and enable successful exploitation of the project results, the AI4DI consortium has created this first draft of the Plan for Use and Dissemination of Foreground, and will continue updating this draft throughout the project’s lifetime. According to the plan, a shared visual identity and online presence was created for the project, and a plan for print-based and publication-based dissemination established. The AI4DI project will be presented in exhibitions, conferences and workshops, where consortium members will actively promote the project and will be involve in networking activities. Besides the activities mentioned above, AI4DI partners are active in many industrial federations, research clusters, and standardization bodies, and will actively help to disseminate the information about the project.

The communication strategy includes scientific results, technology advancements and success stories in industrial use cases and therefore addresses the industry, regulatory bodies, the research community and the wider public by organizing dissemination events, workshops, publications and presentations. A mix of channels and means will ensure that we will reach out to a broad audience and target various interested parties. Communication about the AI4DI project will be adapted and tailored to meet the needs of numerous different audiences beyond the project’s own community. Dissemination and exploitation events will also be used to not only present specific project results but to represent the project in its entirety. Thus, fairs and exhibitions, where any groups of interest will be able to learn more about the AI4DI technologies.

Addressing these dissemination channels will fully achieve further exploitation of project results, since every partner of the consortium will actively participate in these activities and thus ensure the wide spread of information. Exploitation plans for the consortium are reported in the Confidential deliverable “D7.10 Draft Plan for Use of the Foreground”.

The AI4DI consortium has the expertise, connections, and technological value to develop and implement a plan to ensure proper and widespread dissemination, exploitation and communication of the project and its results.

The Draft PUDF is a ‘living document’, therefore the consortium intends to adapt and update this document during the project as required. Its first update was implemented at the end of the first project year.

³ European IPR helpdesk for Horizon2020 (<https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/node/2231>)

8 References

- [1] Funding & tender opportunities Single Electronic Data Interchange Area (SEDIA), Glossary (http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/support/reference_terms.html), accessed 2019/10/22
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- [3] European IPR helpdesk for Horizon2020 (<https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/node/2231>), accessed 2019/10/28

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